

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF HEALTHCARE ORGANIZATIONS IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

One of the priority areas of life of Kazakhstan is the field of information technology, which is aimed at solving the strategic tasks of the state. In the modern conditions of the dominance of information technology (IT), the target state of the medical services sector, which is called "digital medicine" and "digital health care", is of particular importance. Digital transformation is one of the main factors of global economic growth. In this article we observe main advantages of digital transformation in providing healthcare services

Keywords: Digital transformation, digitalization, healthcare management, digitalization in healthcare.

In the development of digitalization of Kazakhstan's healthcare, an important aspect is the formation of optimal conditions for widespread implementation throughout the territory. In this regard, the importance of large state IT corporations in the digitalization of healthcare is growing. Digitalization of Kazakhstan's healthcare is one of the important national development tasks, the solution of which requires balanced and thoughtful management thinking to make informed decisions.

Currently, the use of artificial intelligence systems is considered one of the most promising areas in medicine, moreover, the use of automated systems makes it possible to facilitate and speed up the work of a diagnostician, saving time for more creative processes [1]. In neuro-oncology, digital pathology methods are increasingly used and many institutions have already implemented automated programs for assessing the level of proliferative activity of benign and malignant tumors.

Digital healthcare is a sub-sector of healthcare that, in combination with organizational, legal, economic, medical, scientific and technical measures, on the basis of medical organizations of all levels and forms of ownership, additionally ensures the preservation and strengthening of public health, including the provision of medical care. Digital healthcare includes the use of information and communication technologies for healthcare, including patient treatment, scientific research, training of healthcare workers, disease tracking and public health monitoring. The functioning of digital healthcare is aimed primarily at implementing government support measures for the development of digital medicine, its ecosystem and digital transformation [2].

In turn, as a result of the digital transformation of medicine, scientists define digital medicine as a system of scientific knowledge and practical activities for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases, maintaining and strengthening the health and ability to work of people, prolonging life, as well as alleviating suffering from physical and mental ailments based on a digital healthcare platform that accumulates, maintains and develops a system of scientific knowledge in the field of medicine and access to medical services based on information and communication technologies. Based on

the development of digital medicine, which offers a whole segment of medical gadgets for healthy people and patients (thermometers, pedometers, medical bracelets and much more), a number of conditions for its development have been formed:

— modern digital technologies are actively being introduced into the healthcare sector;

— complex medical equipment is used to treat patients, robotization of medical treatment processes occurs, which causes an actual reduction in the volume of medical manipulations;

— completely new in-demand treatment methods appear, for example, minimally invasive surgery, causing minimal trauma to the patient during surgery and reducing the necessary recovery period;

— there is a widespread digitalization of patient data and the entire medical and preventive institution [3].

The concept of "medical information systems" is the basis of the entire IT infrastructure of an organization and is a set of software and hardware, databases and knowledge necessary for the automation and digitalization of all document flow, for the prompt formation of information flows for the optimal functioning of all processes occurring in medical and preventive institutions.

Most foreign and domestic scientists in their studies have confirmed the medical and social effectiveness of telemedicine, which is based on increasing the availability of medical care and organizing remote patient monitoring. The term "Telemedicine", introduced by T. Bird and R. Mark in the 1970s, is distinguished by its ability to combine telecommunications and information technologies in healthcare. Within the framework of the policy of the World Health Organization, the concept of "telemedicine" has been established, including clinical and educational areas. In Russian and foreign practice, scientists define telemedicine as a healthcare tool that uses telecommunications and electronic information technologies for remote data exchange in real time in order to provide medical care and services at the point of need (in cases where the geographic distance between the health worker and the patient is a critical factor) [4].

The interests of healthcare have also affected supranational bodies. Thus, the World Health Organization of the UN is engaged in collecting and analyzing information on national digital healthcare programs, on the basis of which reviews are formed and published. In addition, a standard model is being developed based on a systemic approach to the digital transformation of healthcare, with the help of which the process of digitalization of medicine will save a significant amount of money on its implementation.

Digital transformation is one of the main factors of global economic growth. Modern medical, social and economic efficiency of providing electronic services remain a subject of discussion among scientists and researchers-practitioners. However, despite the obvious success of a number of federal and regional telemedicine projects, the mass introduction of electronic health methods into the practical activities of most healthcare institutions in Kazakhstan remains problematic. In the information aspect, the service for making an appointment with a doctor is fully functioning in most regions. Only certain regions purchase software in the healthcare sector and mainly at the expense of budgetary funds.

The digital transformation of the healthcare services sector is supported at the state level, since the healthcare system requires modernization and development of new innovative digital healthcare systems based on new technologies and management methods in modern conditions. As of the beginning of 2022, about 120 different software products are used to informatize public healthcare in Kazakhstan.

The healthcare informatization strategy is also implemented at the regional level. Kazakhstan's regions differ significantly in the level of healthcare informatization. It is worth noting the factors that hinder digital development in the regions: the persistence of digital inequality in sparsely populated areas; low level of use of state and municipal services in electronic form; insufficient number of qualified personnel in the region; lack of financial resources for the implementation of projects for the introduction of new digital solutions.

At the same time, a high level of digitalization requires trained personnel. The number and qualifications of these personnel depend, in turn, on the development of science, on the possibilities of their reproduction, arising from demography, as well as on current trends in the digitalization of medicine in general, on related personnel - in the field of IT, on the development of science and the corresponding infrastructure. Another, no less important problem of the digitalization of healthcare is the current state of the information security system [5].

The strategy of digital transformation of Kazakhstani healthcare is aimed, first of all, at creating conditions for increasing the efficiency of activities in the sphere of providing medical services through the introduction of digital technologies. Optimization of the development of digital transformation is carried out by ensuring equal access to the Internet and cellular communications for the country's population, reengineering public services and services for receiving medical ser-

vices taking into account the capabilities of digital technologies, developing and implementing industry platform solutions at the national level, creating a single space for exchanging medical data of patients at all stages of service provision, modernizing the unified state information system in the field of healthcare to create the possibility of quick access to primary medical care, increasing high-speed information exchange in medical organizations.

Healthcare is organized differently around the world and moves at different speeds depending on the country, its legal framework, policy activities, role in the healthcare ecosystem and specific goals of digital transformation in each specific context: from increasing patient-centeredness in hospitals and improving working conditions to new ways of delivering care, such as remote health monitoring using IT technologies.

The development of healthcare digitalization requires significant government intervention due to a number of reasons: the low level of medical personnel in Kazakhstan compared to the total population; migration of healthcare scientists abroad; low demographic indicators in the 1990s, which led to a significant decline in birth rates during this period, which was reflected in the decrease in the number of young professionals in the healthcare sector since the 2010s; imperfections of the regulatory framework in this area.

Despite the fact that Kazakhstan has a problem with the integration of information resources and systems, it is in the healthcare sector that significant changes have recently occurred, especially in the regulatory sphere. The documents adopted by the government and the Ministry of Health regulate the activities of medical institutions and organizations, doctors and patients operating in the digital medical field. The stage of regulatory work for the widespread introduction of digital medicine elements into the practice of Russian healthcare is almost complete. The meanings of the basic concepts of "medical information system" and the MIS operator have been defined, a package of requirements for the unification of MIS into a single information resource controlled by the state has been formed, the rights and obligations of participants in telemedicine consultations have been specified. A single state portal of medical resources will significantly increase the functionality of telemedicine technologies.

In order to develop digital technologies in medicine, it is necessary to improve the level of personnel training in this area. To achieve this scientific task, it is necessary to allocate funds to ensure the development of technologies and personnel training, as well as attract investments for these purposes from abroad. For this purpose, it is advisable to implement special grant programs, a target subprogram within the framework of a joint interdepartmental program of two ministries - digital development and the Ministry of Health, the implementation of the obtained result on the basis of leading clinics and the results in the educational process in the training of specialists.

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